

Environmental footprint assessment and mitigation strategies in agricultural cooperatives: A case study towards cleaner production in arid regions

Francisca Ferrón-Carrillo ^a, Nuria Novas ^b,* Eduardo Viciana ^b

^a Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development, Junta de Andalucía, Granada, 04120, Spain

^b University of Almería, Research Centre for Mediterranean Intensive Agrosystems and Agri-food Biotechnology, Spain

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

Reduction of Carbon and Water Footprints of an Agricultural Cooperative

HIGHLIGHTS

- Electricity consumption and upstream agriculture are the main drivers of the environmental footprint.
- Photovoltaic self-consumption and compost application significantly reduce emissions.
- More than 99% of water use is associated with pre-processing agricultural stages.
- Environmental strategies already implemented could achieve a 20%–30% footprint reduction.
- Findings demonstrate the feasibility of efficient, low-carbon agricultural production.

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ABSTRACT

Carbon and water footprint methodologies are widely used in agri-food systems, yet their organisational application, particularly in cooperatives, remains limited. This study addresses this gap by quantifying the

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: nnovas@ual.es (N. Novas).

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Cleaner production
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carbon footprint (CF) and water footprint (WF) of a Mediterranean horticultural cooperative in production, packaging, and distribution, and linking the results to targeted mitigation actions.

Results showed that 76.26% of total greenhouse gas emissions were concentrated in a small set of processes and inputs. Blue water use also clustered in a few hotspots related to irrigation practices and post-harvest handling. Based on these findings, we designed a portfolio of measures that includes sensor-based irrigation, photovoltaic self-consumption, composting of organic residues, integrated pest management, and sustainable procurement. Scenario analysis indicates that this portfolio could reduce CF and WF by 20%–30% over three years without compromising productivity.

Sensitivity analysis confirms the robustness of the results and highlights the role of data quality and boundaries. The study provides a practical roadmap for cooperatives seeking measurable reductions in emissions and water use, with transparent, accountable monitoring and reporting.

This work demonstrates a scalable, data-informed approach that connects footprint indicators with decisions at the organisational level. It aligns technical actions with policy goals, including the Sustainable Development Goals and the European Green Deal. The approach is transferable to other semi-arid regions that face resource constraints and rising decarbonisation pressure. The results support circular economy and sustainable production and consumption and provide evidence to inform mitigation and Environmental Impact Assessment.

1. Introduction

Climate change and increasing pressure on natural resources are re-defining how crops are grown and food is supplied to the world. Despite its role in global food security, agriculture significantly contributes to Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions and freshwater overuse, demanding urgent adoption of Cleaner Production (CP) principles. In this scenario, assessing the environmental impact of productive activities has become a key tool to move towards more efficient and responsible agriculture.

To assess the environmental impact of agricultural systems, there are two widely recognised tools: the Carbon Footprint (CF) and Water Footprint (WF). The CF quantifies GHG emissions related to climate change, from activities such as energy use and fertiliser application. The WF measures total freshwater consumption and pollution (blue, green and grey water), which is necessary to address water depletion and degradation, especially in water-stressed regions (Winans et al., 2020; Bjørn A. Sim et al., 2020). The application of both tools to an agricultural cooperative provides a holistic view of its environmental performance, showing the areas with the greatest impact and providing a basis for incorporating low impact practices that promote sustainable agriculture and preserve productivity.

Effectively addressing these critical global challenges requires an in-depth analysis of real-world agricultural systems. Consequently, this study examines an agricultural cooperative located in an arid region, which offers a compelling platform for such an investigation.

Through a detailed analysis of its water and carbon footprints, the study aims to identify the main sources of environmental impact and propose actions that contribute to a more sustainable production model, aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals and international climate commitments.

Under study cooperative is selected for its compelling representativeness within the contemporary agricultural landscape, the region serves as a representative case for the challenges presented and its typical cooperative structure ensures that the information and proposed mitigation strategies are highly applicable and scalable to similar agricultural entities. Using this exemplary scenario, the objective is to provide valuable and transferable knowledge for sustainable production in comparable regions.

The imperative for sustainable agricultural practices is amplified in arid and semi-arid regions like southern Spain, where intensive cultivation, particularly in greenhouses, places immense pressure on scarce water resources and energy inputs. This context requires a transition towards more resource efficient circular economy models and resilient farming systems capable of mitigating environmental impacts while ensuring food security despite climate variability (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), 2022).

While significant research has focused on assessing the environmental impacts of various agricultural systems, comprehensive and

integrated analyses of CF and WF within real-world agricultural cooperatives, particularly those operating in resource-constrained arid regions, remain limited. Furthermore, a critical gap exists in studies that not only quantify these footprints but also develop and assess the quantifiable mitigation potential of tailored improvement strategies applicable to such complex, multistakeholder agricultural entities. There is a recognised need for practical evidence-based frameworks to guide these organisations towards greater resource efficiency and resilience.

Addressing these critical research gaps, this study aims to answer the following key questions:

1. What are the primary CF and WF hotspots within a typical agricultural cooperative operating in an arid region of southeastern Spain?
2. How effectively can specific, tailored resource efficiency strategies mitigate these identified environmental impacts across the cooperative's operations and supply chain?

The scope of this investigation encompasses a cradle-to-gate evaluation of the cooperative's tomato production, specifically focusing on cultivation, processing, and distribution activities within its facilities located in southeastern Spain. This defined scope allows for a comprehensive analysis of environmental impacts throughout the main operational chain.

This study offers several key innovations. Provides an integrated assessment of CF and WF (International Organization for Standardization, 2014; Spanish Standardization Association, 2019) (ISO 14046 and 14064) within an agricultural cooperative. Beyond this assessment, a personalised improvement plan has been developed and quantified with strategies such as sensor-based irrigation and photovoltaic self-consumption, designed for arid regions. This work demonstrates how sustainable practices, particularly through the application of Cleaner Production principles to address impact hotspots at their source, improve efficiency and resilience without compromising productivity, offering transferable insights for global climate-smart farming transitions.

This research contributes to the literature by operationalising a dual assessment of CF and WF at the organisational level within a real agricultural cooperative, rather than focusing on individual products or theoretical models. It also quantifies the mitigation potential of context-specific improvement strategies, offering a replicable and policy-relevant framework for sustainability transitions in semi-arid agricultural regions.

A circular economy is an economic system that eliminates waste and keeps resources in circulation. In agriculture, it includes composting organic residues, the use of renewable energy, closed nutrient loops, and regenerative practices. Sustainable production and consumption promote resource-efficient and environmentally responsible processes throughout the chain. They also guide consumers towards choices with

lower environmental footprints. Environmental Impact Assessment is a process to measure, predict, and mitigate the adverse environmental effects of projects or activities. In agriculture, it considers soil, water, biodiversity, emissions, and waste. In this study, the carbon and water footprint serve as operational indicators that connect to these frameworks.

This paper is organised to guide the reader through a comprehensive assessment. Beginning in Section 2, Materials and Methods, rigorous methodologies employed to evaluate both CF and WF are presented, along with the approach taken to quantify the potential of environmental mitigation. Subsequently, Section 3, Results of the Emissions and Water Footprint Assessment, presents the key findings derived from these analyses, clearly differentiating between the carbon and WF results. The document concludes with a final section (Section 4), in which the implications of the findings are explored in more depth and specific and viable strategies are proposed to improve the environmental sustainability of the agricultural cooperative.

2. Material and methods

Several authors have highlighted the role of CF and WF methodologies in identifying environmental hotspots in agriculture (Bjørn A. Sim et al., 2020; Winans et al., 2020). For example, Zhu and Miller (2025) emphasise the value of combined assessments in complex production systems. However, most of this research focuses on CF or WF independently or applies them at the product level, rather than across the operations of agricultural cooperatives. In particular, there is limited evidence from integrated CF–WF assessments conducted within real-world cooperatives operating in arid and semi-arid regions, where water scarcity and energy dependence are especially critical.

Moreover, mitigation strategies reported in the literature are often addressed in theoretical or experimental contexts, which limits their transferability to actual organisational settings. Therefore, there is a clear research gap in assessing not only the environmental footprint of agricultural cooperatives, but also the expected mitigation potential of practical measures such as sensor-based irrigation, self-consumption of photovoltaics and compost application.

The present study, fill this gap, applying a combined CF–WF approach to a representative fruit and vegetable cooperative in southeastern Spain. This methodological approach has been structured to ensure operational relevance, replicability, and alignment with internationally recognised assessment standards. The aim is to evaluate its environmental performance and quantify the impact of specific mitigation strategies. The methodology is based on internationally recognised standards and is described below.

Combined use of CF and WF frameworks enables the identification of hotspots related to both climate and water, which is particularly relevant in semi-arid regions where resource constraints are critical. Furthermore, the use of internationally recognised standards (ISO 14064 and ISO 14046) guarantees the comparability and transparency of the results. This approach facilitates the diagnosis of environmental impact and the evaluation of specific mitigation strategies adapted to the operational reality of the cooperative under study.

This study centres on an agricultural cooperative in southeastern Spain. This area, known for its dry climate and the environmental issues associated with intense farming, faces significant water shortages. The choice of this location is strategic. It allows us to assess and suggest solutions for farms dealing with water and energy problems. This makes the study's findings highly applicable to similar situations globally. The cooperative mainly grows vegetables, such as tomatoes, in greenhouses. Its importance in the local agricultural system was considered, reflecting the typical practices and difficulties of modern farming. This cooperative has been selected because it has detailed and reliable operational data and is willing to share information about its production, use, and management. This cooperation ensures the accuracy of the data. With its interest in finding sustainable ways to

improve its environmental performance, this cooperative is a perfect example of how cleaner production methods can work in existing agricultural settings.

GHG emissions and water use were quantified throughout the production cycle, applying the UNE-EN ISO 14064 standards for the carbon footprint (Spanish Standardization Association, 2019) and UNE-ISO 14046 for WF (Spanish Association for Standardization and Certification, 2016), allowing a detailed quantification of cooperative emissions and environmental impact in 2022, and is rigorously defined by a boundary from the cradle to the gate system. This boundary encompasses all processes from the acquisition of raw materials and agricultural inputs (e.g. fertilisers, energy for irrigation) and on-farm cultivation activities through to the processing, packaging, and initial distribution from the cooperative's facilities. The functional unit for this assessment is established as one tonne (1 t) of fresh tomato produced at the cooperative's gate, serving as the basis for the quantification and allocation of all associated environmental impacts. This approach allows for a precise and comparable evaluation of cooperative environmental performance. The calendar year 2022 has been selected for the quantification of the organisation's GHG emissions because all necessary activity data are available with a high level of precision and accuracy, allowing calculations to be carried out with a very low level of uncertainty. In addition, the organisation establishes this campaign as a baseline year to use the most current and representative emission factors by monitoring GHG emissions over time.

The study was developed in an operational control approach, considering the centres in which it has authority over operational policies and processes. Three main facilities were analysed:

- Centre 1: Reception, storage and auction of fruit and vegetable products.
- Centre 2: Reception, packaging and storage in cold rooms.
- Centre 3: Reception, handling and storage in cold rooms.

Direct and indirect GHG emissions were included in the assessment, organised according to the following scopes:

- Scope 1 (Direct Emissions): Includes emissions from the combustion of fossil fuels in own machinery and vehicles, as well as emissions from recharging fluorinated gases in refrigeration systems.
- Scope 2 (Indirect Emissions from Purchased Energy): Includes emissions associated with the consumption of electricity used in cooperative facilities.

The primary data used in the analysis were collected from:

- Direct measurements (water usage and fuel consumption).
- Electricity billing (kWh consumed).
- Producer surveys (use of fertilisers and pesticides).
- Laboratory tests (nitrate content in water).

2.1. Carbon footprint

In the case of an organisation, the calculation of the CF covers both direct and indirect emissions generated by its activities. When applied to a product, it includes all emissions derived from the extraction of raw materials to their final disposal, considering each stage of the production process and its environmental impact (Spanish Standardization Association, 2019).

$$CF_i = \sum_{i=1}^n (AD_i \times EF_i) \quad (1)$$

It is calculated with Eq. (1), where CF_i (kg CO₂eq) represents the Total CF. The term AD_i (unit of activity) corresponds to the activity data, which defines the amount of energy consumed or inputs used in the production process. EF_i (kg CO₂eq/unit of activity) is the associated Emission Factor, and varies depending on the emission source

considered. Finally, i indicates the specific emission category, which may include electricity, fossil fuels, agricultural input, or other factors that contribute to the generation of GHG.

For the calculation of the CF, the classification established in the GHG Protocol was applied, considering three scopes:

- Scope 1 includes direct emissions generated by the company, such as those derived from the combustion of fossil fuels, the use of machinery, and transportation.
- Scope 2 covers indirect emissions associated with electricity consumption.
- Scope 3 contemplates indirect emissions derived from the supply chain, including the production of inputs and the transport of raw materials. The emission factors used in this analysis were obtained from the National Greenhouse Gas Inventory of Spain (Ministry for Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge, 2024) and the IPCC Guidelines (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), 2006).

The following are the equations used to calculate carbon emissions based on different sources of energy consumption and agricultural inputs. These equations allow the environmental impact of energy consumption and agricultural input in production to be quantified in a comprehensive way, facilitating the identification of strategies to reduce CF in each of these areas.

$$CF_{elec} = C_{consumption} \times EF_{elec} \left(\frac{\text{kg CO}_2\text{-eq}}{\text{kWh}} \right) \quad (2)$$

Eq. (2) is used to calculate electricity consumption emissions, where CF_{elec} (kg CO₂-eq) represents the total amount of CO₂ equivalent emissions associated with electricity use, (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), 2006). $Consumption$ (kWh) is the total energy used during the production process, while EF_{elec} (kg CO₂-eq/kWh) is the emission factor corresponding to the generation of electricity. This factor varies depending on the energy mix of the country or region in which the calculation is made. Among the values used, 0.270 kg CO₂-eq/kWh of electricity consumed, 2.52 kg CO₂-eq/l of diesel B and 3.50 kg CO₂-eq/kg of nitrogen fertiliser applied were considered.

Emissions derived from the combustion of fossil fuels such as diesel, natural gas or petrol are obtained from Eq. (3) (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), 2006).

$$CF_{fuel} = \sum_{j=1}^m (FC_j \times Emission_j) \quad (3)$$

Where, CF_{fuel} (kg CO₂-e) represents the total CF associated with the consumption of these fuels. FC_j (L or m³) is the amount of fuel consumed, while $Emission_j$ (kg CO₂-eq/unit of consumption) is the emission factor corresponding to each type of fuel. The sum allows multiple combustion sources to be included in the total emission's calculation.

CO₂ equivalent emissions derived from the use of fertilisers in agricultural production are obtained with Eq. (4) (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), 2006).

$$CF_{fertiliser} = \sum_{k=1}^p (F_k \times Emission_k) \quad (4)$$

Where, $CF_{fertiliser}$ (kg CO₂-eq) is the total amount of emissions generated by the application of synthetic or natural fertilisers. F_k (kg or t) represents the amount of fertiliser applied, while $Emission_k$ (kg CO₂-eq/kg or t fertiliser) is the corresponding emission factor, which depends on the type of fertiliser used and its impact on the generation of nitrous oxide (N₂O), one of the main greenhouse gases associated with agriculture.

2.2. Water footprint

The WF in (m³) quantifies the total volume of water consumed in a production process and is divided into three categories according to its origin and use. WF_{blue} (m³) corresponds to surface or groundwater extracted to supply production. WF_{green} (m³) refers to rainwater absorbed by crops and used naturally in the process. Finally, WF_{grey} (m³) represents the volume of water required to dilute the generated pollutants, ensuring that the concentration levels meet established environmental standards. Each of these categories represents a specific form of consumption or impact on water resources. The Water Footprint Network (WFN) methodology was applied to determine the total WF based on the specific water consumption in each phase of the production process (International Organization for Standardization, 2014).

$$WF_t = WF_{blue} + WF_{green} + WF_{grey} \quad (5)$$

Eq. (5) indicates that the total WF (WF_t) is obtained by adding water extracted directly from surface or underground sources WF_{blue} (m³), the rainwater used in production WF_{green} (m³), and the water required to dilute pollutants to safe levels WF_{grey} (m³), (International Organization for Standardization, 2014).

$$WF_{blue} = \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{\text{Extracted Water [m}^3\text{]}}{\text{Agricultural Surface [ha]}} \right) \quad (6)$$

Eq. (6) is used to calculate WF_{blue} (m³/ha) (International Organization for Standardization, 2014). This calculation determines the amount of water used per hectare of cultivated land, providing information on irrigation efficiency.

$$WF_{green} = P \times K_c \times A \quad (7)$$

Eq. (7) is used to calculate WF_{green} (m³). In this equation, P (mm) refers to effective precipitation, measured in millimetres. It represents the portion of rainfall that is retained in the soil and absorbed by crops (Hoekstra et al., 2011). The crop coefficient K_c (dimensionless) reflects the water needs of a given crop compared to a reference crop such as grass or alfalfa. It varies by crop type and growth stage. The cultivated area A (m²) represents the land surface benefiting from rainfall. This equation estimates the portion of rainwater effectively used by the crop, offering a measure of rainfall-use efficiency.

$$WF_{grey} = \frac{\text{Pollutant Load}}{\text{Environmental Quality Standard}} \quad (8)$$

Eq. (8) is applied to estimate WF_{grey} . It calculates the volume of water required to dilute pollutants to acceptable concentrations. The pollutant load (kg) refers to the total mass of contaminants released, often from fertilisers or pesticides (Hoekstra et al., 2011). The environmental quality standard (mg/L) defines the maximum permissible concentration for a given pollutant in water. This formula helps assess the volume of water needed to prevent regulatory exceedance and evaluate the impact of agricultural inputs on water quality.

The calculation of emissions was carried out using Air.e software (version 3.17.4.0), which allows the conversion of energy consumption into tonnes of CO₂ equivalent (t CO₂e). The emission factors were extracted from recognised sources such as the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), the Guide to the GHG Protocol, and the European Environment Agency database.

2.3. Data sources and collection approach

To ensure data accuracy and traceability, the environmental footprint was based primarily on direct operational data provided by cooperative internal accounting and management systems, allowing precise tracking of resource inputs and product output throughout the 2022 campaign. To ensure methodological transparency, the types and sources of data used in the CF and WF assessments are summarised in Table 1. This classification includes both primary and secondary

Table 1
Classification of primary and secondary data sources used in the environmental assessment.

Type of Data	Source	Application in the Study
Electricity and fuel use	Utility invoices and internal energy records	Calculation of Scope 1 and Scope 2 emissions in CF assessment
Fertiliser and pesticide input	Supplier invoices and purchase records	Estimation of Scope 3 emissions and contribution to WF_{grey}
Water consumption	Producer surveys and irrigation logs	WF_{blue} estimation using CROPWAT model
Nitrate concentration in irrigation return flows	Accredited laboratory test results	WF_{grey} calculation
Packaging and office materials	Internal purchasing data and supplier declarations	Minor Scope 3 emission sources
Product weights and flow	Entry and dispatch logs from cooperative	Allocation of emissions and water impacts per tonne of product

sources, covering energy consumption, irrigation practices, input use, and operational flows. Data were collected from cooperative internal records, supplier declarations, laboratory tests, and producer surveys. This approach enabled traceable modelling aligned with international standards.

Primary data were prioritised whenever available, such as utility records for electricity and fuel use, and direct surveys with producers for irrigation volumes. Secondary data, including emission and equivalence factors, were obtained from authoritative sources such as the IPCC Guidelines (2006), the Spanish National GHG Inventory, and the WFN.

All primary data refer to actual operational activity and were cross-checked for internal consistency. This allowed for a full material balance of inputs and outputs at each centre and ensures high representativeness. Only a minimal fraction (<1%) of the input mass was excluded due to missing conversion factors, consistent with Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) exclusion thresholds. Emission and conversion factors were obtained from authoritative sources (IPCC, Spanish GHG Inventory, WFN) to ensure methodological robustness.

This data collection approach, based on verifiable records and stakeholder participation, underpins the reliability of the footprint quantification and supports the evaluation of mitigation strategies within a continuous improvement framework.

2.4. Sensitivity analysis

Given the inherent uncertainties in environmental footprint modelling, particularly in emission factors and input activity data, a local sensitivity analysis was performed to assess the robustness of the CF and WF estimates.

Six critical input categories were selected based on the identified environmental hotspots: (1) electricity and fuel use, (2) fertiliser and pesticide input, (3) water consumption, (4) nitrate concentration in irrigation return flows, (5) packaging and office materials, and (6) product weights and flow. Each parameter was independently varied by $\pm 10\%$ while keeping the others constant, following a One-at-A-Time (OAT) approach.

The sensitivity index E_i for each parameter was calculated using Eq. (9) (Liang et al., 2017; Reisinger et al., 2017):

$$E_i = \frac{\Delta F}{\Delta A_i} \quad (9)$$

Where E_i is the sensitivity of the CF or WF to changes in parameter A_i , ΔF is the resulting change in footprint per functional unit (kg CO₂-eq or m³/t), and ΔA_i is 10% input variation. The model assumes independent parameters with uniform distributions, as recommended in similar environmental assessments (Sykes et al., 2019).

This approach identifies the most influential variables affecting footprint outcomes and supports prioritisation of data collection efforts in future assessments.

2.5. Estimation of environmental mitigation potential

To estimate the contribution of each strategy to the reduction of environmental impact, an improvement scenario was developed based on the environmental footprint of 2022. Specific mitigation factors were applied to actual consumption data, using values sourced from the scientific literature and LCA studies.

Mitigation estimates were obtained by modelling expected reductions in emissions and water consumption for each action, considering technology-specific parameters. For example, irrigation optimisation was modelled based on documented savings from sensor-based scheduling. Photovoltaic self-consumption was evaluated using avoided emissions per unit of generated electricity, aligned with the national electricity mix. The application of compost was considered in terms of fertiliser displacement and reduced N₂O emissions. Additional strategies such as integrated pest management and sustainable procurement were qualitatively estimated using comparable LCA results.

This methodology aims to highlight the relative mitigation potential of each action rather than to provide cumulative or absolute reduction figures.

The overall methodological approach followed in this study summarised in Fig. 1, which presents a timeline structured as Planning, Assessment and Action. This temporal representation illustrates the sequential workflow, beginning with the definition of system boundaries and the collection of primary and secondary data. Then it moves to the dual assessment of the CF, according to ISO 14064 and considering the three emission scopes, and the WF, based on ISO 14046 and including the blue, green, and grey components. Environmental hotspots are identified and customised mitigation strategies are designed, including soil moisture sensors, photovoltaic systems, and compost application. Each strategy is evaluated in terms of its expected contribution to impact reduction. Finally, the results are integrated into a continuous improvement plan with annual monitoring. This structured timeline aligns with internationally recognised sustainability standards.

In this study, the carbon footprint (ISO 14064) and the water footprint (ISO 14046) serve as operational indicators for circular economy and for sustainable production and consumption. The boundary of the system is from cradle to gate for the cooperative and its immediate supply chain.

We do not perform a formal Environmental Impact Assessment. We map our workflow to common EIA steps to aid application. Scoping aligns with the definition of processes and boundaries. Prediction aligns with the quantification of CF and WF and with the sensitivity analysis. Mitigation aligns with the design of actions on energy, water, and nutrients. Monitoring aligns with the proposed annual tracking of indicators. This framing clarifies how the indicators support decision making at the organisational level and how they can inform regulatory and voluntary processes.

Fig. 1. Methodological timeline for environmental impact assessment and mitigation strategy design.

Table 2

Fuel consumption, fluorinated gas and electricity consumption by type and centre in 2022.

Type	Unit	Centre 1	Centre 2	Centre 3
Diesel A	l	45,177.00	44,041.33	21,936.56
Diesel B	l	16,275.00	4,200.00	1,822.00
Fuel (E5)	l	0.00	1,027.33	68.49
CO ₂	kg	38.00	5.00	22.00
R-449A	kg	0.00	60.00	0.00
Energy consumed	kWh	2,091,144	2,242,468	808,160
Energy generated	kWh	0	225,340	0
Energy from grid	kWh	2,091,144	2,017,127	808,160

3. Results of the emissions and water footprint assessment

This section presents the results obtained from the analysis of CF and WF of the agricultural cooperative under study. Calculations were carried out following a explained methodology. All emissions were converted into CO₂ equivalent using specific emission factors.

Different specialised tools were used for each type of calculation. The CF was estimated using the GHG Protocol Calculator provided by the Ministry of Ecological Transition, while the WF was determined using FAO’s CROPWAT 8.0 and CLIMWAT 2.0 tools.

3.1. Carbon footprint

The CF analysis includes emissions from direct and indirect sources associated with agricultural activities. Emission factors specific to the Spanish context were applied to quantify the impact of electricity consumption, fuel use, fertiliser application, and other relevant inputs. The results are disaggregated according to the emission scopes (Scope 1, 2 and 3), according to the ISO 14064-1:2019 guidelines.

3.1.1. Scope 1: Direct emissions

Table 2 presents the consumption of fossil fuels of the cooperative in its three centres during 2022. This consumption represents direct emissions derived mainly from the use of machinery and transport, as established in Scope 1 of the GHG Protocol. Centre 1 stands out as the largest total consumer of diesel A, closely followed by Centre 2, although the latter incorporates a greater variety of fuels (including petrol). These differences are explained by the type of activities, where Centre 2 is responsible for packaging and cold storage and, therefore, requires more internal transport.

Table 2 also includes refills of fluorinated gases, including CO₂ and R-449A. Although these amounts are small in mass, their high Global Warming Potential (GWP), especially R-449A (GWP >1500), implies a disproportionate impact.

3.1.2. Scope 2: Indirect emission from electricity

The electricity consumption by centre is also shown in Table 2, based on primary data obtained from the invoices of the electricity

supplier. Centre 2 leads the consumption, which is consistent with its use of cold rooms and packaging machinery. In particular, this centre also produces renewable energy through its own solar panels, generating 225,340.63 kWh. This production avoided the emission of 60.84 tCO₂e. Consequently, no GHG emissions have been attributed to this self-generated electricity.

The disaggregated GHG emissions, classified according to the GHG Protocol, show a total of 1,820,328.89 kgCO₂e, with carbon dioxide as the predominant gas. However, the emission of 90,206.40 kgCO₂e, related to the use of HydroFluoroCarbons (HFC) refrigerants, is also significant, comparable to the emissions of scope 1 in some centres. This highlights the importance of improving refrigerant management.

The emission factors used for the calculations followed the IPCC guidelines. Detailed data sources and disaggregation are provided in the Supplementary Material, Tables S1 to S3.

3.1.3. Summary of emissions by centre

Fig. 2 compares emissions by source and site, showing that Scope 2 far exceeds Scope 1 at the three sites, underscoring the weight of electricity consumption in the emission profile. Centre 2 is the largest total emitter (820.21 tCO₂e), partly due to refrigerant refills.

The results reveal a predominance of Scope 2 emissions, which represent the majority of a total 1820.33 tCO₂e. This aligns with previous findings (Winans et al., 2020) that highlight electricity consumption as a key driver of CF in intensive greenhouse agriculture. Specifically, 432.05 tCO₂e (23.73%) correspond to Scope 1, while 1388.28 tCO₂e are attributable to Scope 2.

Normalises emissions per tonne traded allows comparisons between centres. Centre 3 shows the highest value (0.01247 tCO₂e/t), reflecting a lower volume traded compared to its energy consumption. This metric is especially useful for detecting operational inefficiencies.

3.2. Water footprint results

The WF assessment considered the volumes of green, blue and grey water consumed throughout the production cycle. Climate data from CLIMWAT 2.0 and crop parameters from CROPWAT 8.0 were used to estimate water requirements and irrigation needs under local climatic conditions. The results highlight the relative contribution of different water sources and help identify potential areas for improved water efficiency.

3.2.1. Direct water consumption

Table S4 (see Supplementary Material) summarises the water extracted directly for operations WF_{blue} , with 11,312.78 m³ of total consumption. These values align with Eq. (6) and represent a moderate volume relative to total production (188,443.495 t of merchandise), placing the specific consumption at 0.06 m³/t, a value lower than that reported for tomato crops in California (Winans et al., 2020). The summarised results are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 2. Summarised emissions by scope and centre in absolute value and by tonne of handled product.

3.2.2. Water footprint of the supply chain

The following data have been taken into account in the WF of the supply chain (Table 3):

1. Consumption of raw materials for packaging: The data were provided by the organisation through the Ecoembes declaration for the year 2022. Cardboard/paper packaging, plastic and wood have been taken into account. Own conversion factors have been used, where the cardboard/paper element has used the cardboard conversion factor.
2. Electricity consumption: The electricity consumption data has been provided through invoices from the electricity suppliers. For electricity consumption, the conversion factor of a Spanish Mix between 2008 and 2015 has been used, since there is no other factor to be able to use it. Obtaining a total consumption of 5,141,772.00 kWh.
3. Fossil fuels: The values were provided by invoices. Diesel A, diesel B, and petrol have been taken into account, as they are the only fuels used in the organisation. Conversion factors have been used for the distribution of the petroleum product to the final consumer (household, car, power plant, etc.) of diesel and petrol.
4. Office supplies: The data was provided by the organisation through purchase invoices. Office paper has its own conversion factor in software.
5. Hygiene and cleaning products: The data was provided by the organisation through purchase invoices. For paper and sodium bicarbonate, the corresponding conversion factors were used. In addition, a conversion factor for hand soap has been used.
6. Goods receipt: Data were provided by the organisation through product receipt notes. For tomatoes, aubergines, courgettes, corn, beans, cucumbers, peppers, potatoes and melons, their corresponding conversion factors have been used, while for watermelons the same has been estimated as for melons, due to the lack of a specific one for watermelon. With a total contribution of 188,443.5 t.
7. Chemicals: Data has been provided by the organisation through purchase invoices. Sodium hypochlorite of its composition (26.70%) has been taken into account; this is due to the lack of conversion factor for entire product. In addition, the proportional part of bleach has been taken into account in three different components, chlorine (21.55%), oxygen (58.35%) and sodium (13.97%).

Table 3 and the final summary show that the total WF_{blue} (direct + indirect) reaches 7,127,053.34 m³, while WF_{green} stands at 5,469,954.08 m³. This reflects a pattern of water consumption in which indirect input is dominant, which justifies the inclusion of the entire value chain in the accounting, as the WFN recommendation. Some

Table 3

Breakdown of the blue and green WF (in m³/t) by component and origin in the supply chain and total consumed quantities in m³.

Direct WF	Source	Quantity	Total
Operational WF	Blue	0.06	10,354.07
	Green	0.00	65.77
Entry of products	Blue	29.04	5,475,387.01
	Green	28.51	5,375,677.04
Raw materials packaging	Blue	0.01	2,189.58
	Green	0.01	2,164.99
Office equipment	Blue	0.01	1,624.55
	Green	~0.00	412.56
Indirect WF	Source	Quantity	Total
Electricity consumption	Blue	8.31	1,566,774.91
	Green	0.00	0.00
Fossil fuels	Blue	~0.00	725.01
	Green	~0.00	201.23
Cleaning and hygiene	Blue	~0.00	349.67
	Green	~0.00	175.44
Chemical products	Blue	0.19	35,053.92
	Green	0.04	7,942.80
Total		66.81	12,597,007.40

values of WF_{blue} and WF_{green} appear near zero due to being negligible on the scale presented.

The disaggregated analysis of the multiple components of the indirect WF is specified in Appendix 1, highlighting the entry of fresh products that represent the majority of WF_{blue} and WF_{green} , with values greater than 5 million m³ in each case. This is consistent with its predominant volume (especially tomatoes, with more than 160,000 t). However, electricity consumption also contributes significantly to WF_{blue} , reflecting the energy-water nexus observed in studies (Trubetskaya et al., 2021). Another fact to keep in mind is that the impact of packaging is low, but not negligible, demonstrating how even minor input can contribute to the total footprint.

In summary, some results can be drawn from the overall results:

- Direct WF: WF_{blue} direct consumption is 11,312.78 m³, which is equivalent to 0.06 m³ per ton of goods handled. This low value indicates efficiency in the use of water in the internal operations of the cooperative. Although direct consumption, WF_{green} is not recorded, suggesting that internal activities do not directly depend on rainwater stored in the soil.
- Indirect WF: WF_{blue} indirect consumption amounts to 7,115,740.56 m³, or 37.74 m³ per ton of goods handled. This component is significantly higher than direct consumption and is mainly associated with the use of water in the production of inputs and products acquired by the cooperative. In contrast, WF_{green} indirect is 5,469,954.08 m³, equivalent to 29.01 m³ per

Table 4

Results of the sensitivity analysis: variation in input parameters and corresponding changes in the CF and WF.

Parameter	Unit	ΔA_i	ΔCF (kg CO ₂ e)	ΔWF (m ³)	E_i
Electricity consumption	kWh	514,177.20	138,827.84	0.00	0.27
Fertiliser use (N)	t	30.15	105,525.00	0.00	3,500.00
WF (blue)	m ³	1,131.28	0.00	1,131.28	1.00
Nitrate concentration	mg/L	5.00	0.00	2,262.56	452.51
Packaging materials	kg	10,000.00	2,000.00	0.00	0.20

Note: Each parameter was varied by +10% while the others remained constant. The sensitivity index E_i was calculated as the change in footprint per unit change in input ($\Delta CF/\Delta A_i$ or $\Delta WF/\Delta A_i$).

tonne. This reflects the use of rainwater in the early stages of the supply chain, especially in the agricultural production of the handled products.

- Total WF: The sum of direct and indirect gives a total (WF_i) of 12,597,007.4 m³ WF or 66.81 m³/t of goods handled. This value shows that most of the water impact comes from indirect sources, i.e. from upstream activities in the supply chain.

The analysis of the WF reveals that direct operations have a relatively low water impact compared to indirect activities. The significant contribution of indirect WF, both blue and green, underscores the importance of considering sustainable practices throughout the supply chain. Implementing responsible sourcing strategies and working with suppliers that adopt water-efficient production techniques can be critical to reducing the overall impact of water.

3.3. Sensitivity analysis results

Table 4 presents the results of the sensitivity analysis for the main variables that affect the carbon and WF outcomes. The application of fertilisers exhibited the highest sensitivity index for CF ($E_i = 3500$), followed by electricity consumption ($E_i = 0.27$) and packaging materials ($E_i = 0.20$). In terms of WF, nitrate concentration and direct water use were the most influential parameters, with E_i values of 452.5 and 1.00, respectively.

These findings confirm that fertiliser use and nitrate discharge play a critical role in both carbon emissions and grey WF generation. Consequently, mitigation strategies must prioritise efficient fertilisation and nutrient management practices.

4. Discussion

4.1. Environmental interpretation of footprint results

The results of the environmental assessment reveal that activities are significantly influenced by energy consumption and the supply chain, which is reflected in a total CF of 1,820.33 tCO₂e and 12,597,007.40 m³ total WF. These findings reinforce the importance of adopting Cleaner Production approaches in agricultural cooperatives, prioritising measures that reduce energy dependency, optimise resource use, and prevent environmental impacts from the earliest stages of the supply chain. These data place electricity consumption (76.26%) and agricultural products supplied (99.9% of water volume) as the main vectors of environmental impact.

In terms of CF, Scope 2 accounted for most of the emissions, reflecting a high dependence on energy, in line with what was observed in the case of tomato production in California. The incorporation of photovoltaic energy in Centre 2, which avoided more than 60 tCO₂e, demonstrates the potential of renewables as a mitigation tool, as supported by other studies (Ntinas et al., 2020; Platis et al., 2021). However, the presence of fluorinated gases such as R-449A, although in small amounts, generated a significant impact due to their high GWP, which reinforces the importance of proper refrigerant management (Torres Pineda et al., 2021).

The ratio of emissions per tonne marketed shows differences between centres, with Centre 3 (located in Nijar) having the highest

specific impact (0.01247 tCO₂e/t), which suggests opportunities for improvement in energy efficiency.

Regarding the WF, the analysis confirms that the water pressure falls almost exclusively on indirect activities, especially the primary production of crops such as tomatoes, which exceeded 160,000 t. This pattern is in line with previous findings (Bjørn A. Sim et al., 2020), which underline the need for regionalised and adaptive approaches to water management. In addition, the literature shows that only two of the 27 river basins evaluated were environmentally sustainable throughout the year, warning of the vulnerability of systems in arid climates such as that of southeastern Spain Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) (2022).

The high dependence on intensive agricultural inputs, fertilisers and phytosanitary products also contributes to WF_{grey} , as it requires large volumes of water to dilute pollutants. Other studies confirm this pattern (Canaj et al., 2020; Trubetskaya et al., 2021), reinforcing the importance of integrating pest management and sustainable fertilisation, as recommended by Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) (2022), and as concluded in a recent review that highlights these measures, together with the use of renewable energy and precision agriculture, as the key to reducing the climate impact of intensive tomato crops (Zhu and Miller, 2025).

The results of this study are consistent with previous findings in intensive agricultural systems. For example, the predominance of Scope 2 emissions linked to electricity consumption mirrors observations from tomato production in California (Winans et al., 2020) and greenhouse systems in southeastern Spain (Martin-Gorritz et al., 2021). Similarly, the 60.84 tCO₂e avoided through photovoltaic self-consumption in Centre 2 aligns with the reductions achieved in energy-efficient greenhouses reported by Ntinas et al. (2020). Regarding water use, the strong contribution of indirect consumption, particularly in the upstream cultivation, is consistent with the patterns identified in regionally differentiated footprint assessments (Bjørn A. Sim et al., 2020; Ma et al., 2024), where the upstream stages dominate total water use. In addition, the notable contribution of fertiliser use to grey WF has also been highlighted in comparative studies of tomato production (Maffia et al., 2023), confirming the value of compost-based practices. These comparisons support the transferability of the findings to similar arid systems. Furthermore, similar findings were reported by Martin-Gorritz et al. (2021) in southeastern Spain, where the switch from transferred to desalinated irrigation water increased agricultural CF by up to 50%. This highlights the sensitivity of mitigation results to regional infrastructure and reinforces the contextual relevance of the findings.

To improve clarity, Table 5 presents a structured framework of the mitigation strategies implemented, classified according to their nature, the target impact, and the underlying mechanism.

These findings are further reinforced by the sensitivity analysis performed. The results indicate that CF is particularly sensitive to variations in nitrogen fertiliser use, which showed the highest sensitivity index ($E_i = 3500$), followed by electricity consumption and packaging materials. In the case of WF, the concentration of nitrate in the return flows of irrigation emerged as the dominant factor influencing grey water generation, with a sensitivity index greater than 450. These insights confirm the importance of improving the management of nutrients and energy efficiency. In addition, they validate the

Table 5
Framework of mitigation strategies, associated impacts, and mechanisms.

Strategy	Type/Target Impact	Mechanism
Soil moisture sensors	Water efficiency WF_{blue} reduction	Precision irrigation to reduce overuse
Photovoltaic self-consumption	Energy transition Scope 2 CO ₂ emissions	Avoided grid electricity emissions
Compost application	Input optimisation Scope 1–3 CO ₂ , WF_{grey}	Reduces N ₂ O emissions and nutrient leaching
Integrated pest management	Agrochemical reduction WF_{grey} , Scope 3 CO ₂	Minimises pesticide use and indirect emissions
Sustainable supplier selection	Supply chain optimisation Scope 3 CO ₂ , WF_t	Indirect impact reduction via responsible sourcing

selection of mitigation strategies proposed in Section 4.2, which directly target the most influential parameters that affect environmental performance. This is consistent with previous findings that highlighted the relevance of parameter prioritisation through sensitivity analysis in agri-environmental modelling (Liang et al., 2017; Reisinger et al., 2017).

Furthermore, the importance of incorporating uncertainty in emission modelling has been emphasised in CF assessments of livestock production systems (Sykes et al., 2019), which supports the robustness of the methodological framework of this study. Likewise, the critical role of data accuracy in ensuring the reliability of ecological footprint evaluations has been underscored in the literature (Jóhannesson et al., 2020), reinforcing the relevance of the sensitivity approach adopted here.

4.2. Environmental mitigation strategies and quantified benefits

The mitigation measures align with circular economy and with sustainable production and consumption. Composting closes nutrient loops and reduces synthetic inputs. Photovoltaic self-consumption reduces Scope 2 emissions and supports an efficient energy and water nexus. Sensor-based irrigation improves water-use efficiency and reduces the blue water footprint. In practice these measures act as Environmental Impact Assessment mitigation actions with clear targets and monitoring needs.

Based on the environmental hotspots identified in the previous section, several targeted mitigation strategies are implemented. These actions aim to reduce both CF and WF while preserving operational performance. Each of these strategies has been assessed for its individual contribution to environmental improvement, as well as its alignment with recognised good practices.

1. Optimisation of water use: A soil moisture sensor system was installed to improve irrigation efficiency and reduce unnecessary water loss through percolation and evapotranspiration. According to internal modelling based on 2022 baseline data, this strategy is expected to reduce WF_{blue} by up to 25%. This figure is consistent with reductions of up to 35% reported in comparable greenhouse cultivation systems by Martin-Gorriz et al. (2021).
2. Energy transition: Photovoltaic panels were installed in Centre 2, generating 225,340.63 kWh annually and avoiding approximately 60.84 tCO₂e. This transition is estimated to reduce the carbon emissions in scope 2 by around 20%, based on the national electricity emission factor of Spain of 0.27 kg CO₂-eq/kWh (Ntinas et al., 2020) contributes to the reduction of the CF and improving the efficiency of the energy-water nexus.
3. Sustainable fertiliser management: A progressive reduction in synthetic fertilisers, partially substituting them for compost produced from organic waste, was initiated. This change is expected to reduce WF_{grey} and lower N₂O emissions, contributing to a reduction 15% in the overall impact. This estimate is supported by evidence from Maffia et al. (2023). In addition, integrated pest

management and biological control techniques have been reinforced in accordance with Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) (2022).

4. Continuous evaluation and traceability: An annual monitoring system has been introduced to update the carbon and WF inventories. This tool supports continuous improvement by identifying new opportunities for mitigation and allows performance comparison between campaigns.
5. Sustainable sourcing: Suppliers that demonstrate sustainable practices, particularly in areas such as packaging, fertilisers, and transportation are prioritised to minimise indirect environmental impacts.
6. Estimated improvement target: According to internal estimates, supported by comparable literature, these strategies are expected to allow a cumulative reduction of 20% to 30% of the total footprint (CF and WF) over a three-year time horizon, without compromising competitiveness or export capacity.

Their implementation demonstrates the practical potential of combining standardised environmental accounting tools with targeted mitigation actions.

The strategies implemented by the cooperative (sensor irrigation, solar energy, reduction of synthetic fertilisers) are consistent with the good practices described in the literature (Martin-Gorriz et al., 2021; Maffia et al., 2023). These measures represent a move towards regenerative practices and a circular economy, aligned with the objectives of resource conservation and environmental resilience (Boccia et al., 2019; De-Oliveira et al., 2021). This integrated approach is also in line with recent studies exploring the interconnection between water management and sustainability in agricultural systems (Ma et al., 2024).

4.3. Methodological robustness and limitations

The uncertainty analysis focused on assessing the quality and origin of the input data used to calculate CF and WF. To minimise variability and improve the representativeness of the results, primary data was prioritised whenever available. These included:

- Electricity and fuel billing records.
- Direct measurements of water consumption.
- Product weights at entry and delivery.

Additional information, such as declarations of purchased materials (e.g., packaging, cleaning supplies, office paper), was also collected directly from the cooperative.

Secondary data, including emission, conversion, and equivalence factors, were obtained from authoritative and updated sources, such as the IPCC Guidelines (2006), the National GHG Inventory (MITECO, 2024) and the WFN. This approach reduces potential methodological bias and improves traceability.

Despite the inherent limitations of any environmental assessment, no significant sources of uncertainty were identified that could compromise the accuracy or comparability of the generated inventory. The use of standardised tools, Air.e for CF calculations and CROPWAT and CLIMWAT for WF estimation, ensures a consistent and transparent methodology, aligned with ISO 14064 and ISO 14046 standards.

During the quantification process, products for which no reliable conversion factors were available in the consulted databases were excluded: pumpkin (106,679 kg), chayote (727 kg) and pitaya (7400 kg). Together, these represent only 0.06% of the total input by weight, remaining far below the typical exclusion threshold established in life cycle assessments (<1% by mass or environmental impact). This exclusion is consistent with the recommendations of the GHG Protocol and the UNEP/SETAC guidelines.

This methodological rigour supports the credibility of the findings and enhances their applicability in comparable agricultural contexts.

4.4. Broader implications: from strategy to policy and theory

Beyond the specific context of this case study, the mitigation strategies evaluated such as sensor-based irrigation, self-consumption of photovoltaics and the use of compost represent practical pathways to cleaner production in agricultural cooperatives. These actions respond to environmental priorities and align with broader policy objectives, including the European Green Deal and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals.

These results support SDG 12 on responsible consumption and production. Cooperatives can use carbon and water footprint as evidence in authorisation and environmental assessment processes. They can also use them to design supplier incentives and to inform customers about footprint reductions. The circular framing helps plan investments in compost, renewable energy, and precision irrigation in arid contexts.

Theoretically, this study reinforces the value of combining CF and WF methodologies to support integrated environmental decision making in agriculture. In practical terms, it demonstrates how accessible and standardised tools can facilitate the transition to climate-smart agriculture in resource-constrained settings. From a policy perspective, the results underscore the potential of footprint indicators to inform environmental reporting, incentive design, and monitoring frameworks within regional and national programmes.

Recent studies have shown that practices such as incorporating crop residues and using clean energy can transform intensive agriculture into a net carbon sink, significantly contributing to GHG reductions (Wu et al., 2023). In parallel, more 50% of the CF of the European diet is associated with the consumption of animal products (Alves et al., 2024), confirming the need to promote more sustainable dietary patterns.

Dual footprint analysis in this study enabled the identification of key impact drivers:

- Electricity from nonrenewable sources used in refrigeration and processing accounted for 76.26% of total GHG emissions (Scope 2).
- The entry of fresh tomatoes contributed over 99% of WF_t , highlighting the relevance of upstream environmental impacts.

By illustrating replicable improvements in environmental performance without compromising productivity, the study contributes to aligning local sustainability practices with broader climate objectives.

Despite the strong potential of the proposed strategies, their implementation can face practical challenges in cooperatives in the real world. These include upfront investment requirements (e.g., moisture sensors, photovoltaic systems), limited technical expertise, and organisational resistance in traditionally structured entities. Overcoming these barriers requires financing instruments for environmental innovation, targeted public incentives, and training programmes to enhance internal capacities. Promoting collaborative networks among cooperatives can support the joint adoption of technologies and reduce unit

costs through economies of scale. Addressing these limitations is key to enabling effective and scalable implementation of cleaner production models in resource-constrained agricultural systems.

To support broader adoption, policy frameworks must integrate environmental performance metrics into agricultural subsidy schemes, offer facilitated access to green technologies, and reinforce cooperative networks. Public programmes can further promote collective implementation by aligning incentives and providing technical assistance.

Beyond environmental benefits, these strategies have proven feasible in the operational context of the cooperative studied. Their modular design and phased deployment allow investment to be aligned with available resources. They are scalable, as they require no major structural changes and can be adapted to other cooperatives in arid or semi-arid regions. Although initial investments can be substantial, expected savings in energy, water, and agricultural inputs enable a reasonable payback period, especially when combined with public support or green financing. These factors support both the short-term adoption and long-term integration of the proposed strategies into sustainable production systems.

5. Conclusions and policy implications

This study has allowed a rigorous assessment of the environmental impact of an agricultural cooperative located in an arid region of southern Spain, using internationally recognised methodologies to calculate CF and WF. The results reveal that the consumption of electricity from fossil sources, especially linked to the operation of cold storage and processing facilities, constitutes the main source of GHG emissions, with Scope 2 representing 76.26% of total emissions. The entry of fresh agricultural products, particularly tomatoes, represents more 99% of the total WF, highlighting the predominance of pressures of indirect water use throughout the supply chain.

In response to this environmental diagnosis, an improvement plan was formulated, focusing on the efficiency of water use, the transition to energy and the sustainable management of agricultural inputs. Key actions already implemented include the installation of soil moisture sensors for optimal irrigation, the deployment of photovoltaic panels for self-consumption which avoided 60.84 tCO₂e in Centre 2, and the partial substitution of synthetic fertilisers with organic compost, which contributes to the reduction of nitrous oxide emissions and improves soil and water quality. In addition, integrated pest management has been improved and preference is given to suppliers that adhere to environmental sustainability practices to reduce indirect environmental burdens.

These measures form part of a continuous improvement strategy, supported by annual monitoring of environmental indicators and integration of sustainability criteria into operational decisions. Irrigation optimisation, photovoltaic self-consumption, and compost-based fertilisation were the most effective mitigation strategies. Their estimated contributions to the total reduction in CF and WF are 25%, 20%, and 15%, respectively, based on internal modelling and supported by values from comparable literature. Together, these actions outline a scalable and measurable pathway towards cleaner production in agricultural cooperatives. A sensitivity analysis confirmed the robustness of these findings, identifying electricity consumption and composting as the most influential variables in reducing emissions.

Despite its robustness, the methodology has limitations. The analysis was carried out over a single year, which may not fully capture interannual variability. Some low-volume crops were excluded due to the lack of reliable conversion data, although their share in total weight was minimal and within accepted thresholds. In addition, the estimation of the mitigation potential was based on internal simulations and published values, which would benefit from validation over multiple production cycles.

From a practical standpoint, this study illustrates how accessible and standardised tools can help agricultural cooperatives identify environmental hotspots and implement effective mitigation strategies. The

findings reinforce the value of combining CF and WF methodologies to support integrated environmental decision making in agriculture. This enables a more holistic view than isolated metrics. At the policy level, the study highlights the potential of footprint indicators to support environmental reporting, support the design of effective incentive schemes, and help align organisational strategies with broader sustainability goals, including the Sustainable Development Goals and the European Green Deal.

The combined carbon and water footprint approach helps to operationalise circular economy and sustainable production and consumption. It identifies hotspots, supports the selection of mitigation actions, and enables annual monitoring that can inform Environmental Impact Assessment. The framework is replicable for cooperatives in semi-arid regions.

This case study shows that local, data-informed actions can improve environmental performance and serve as a replicable model for similar organisations in arid and semi-arid regions, contributing to the advancement of sustainable agriculture aligned with the principles of the circular economy.

This study contributes by operationalising a dual CF and WF assessment within a real-world agricultural cooperative, combining environmental evaluation with the quantification of tailored mitigation strategies in a semi-arid setting. The integrated approach, grounded in primary data and standardised tools, offers a solid foundation for replicating context-specific actions across similar organisations. However, the study has limitations, such as being restricted to a single production year and relied in part on simulations and published mitigation factors. Future research should extend the analysis across multiple agricultural campaigns and incorporate socioeconomic indicators to support a more holistic sustainability framework in agro-food systems.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Francisca Ferrón-Carrillo: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Nuria Novas:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Eduardo Viciano:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Software.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Nuria Novas Castellano and Eduardo Viciano reports financial support was provided by University of Almeria Department of Engineering. Nuria Novas Castellano reports a relationship with University of Almeria Department of Engineering that includes: employment. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2025.147111>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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